

CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE: THE CURRENT STATE OF THE PROBLEM

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Annotation. In modern society, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), along with arterial hypertension, coronary artery disease (CHD) and diabetes mellitus, is one of the leading chronic diseases; they account for more than 30% of all other forms of human pathology. The World Health Organization (WHO) classifies COPD as a disease with a high level of social burden, and it is widespread in both developed and developing countries. According to the WHO experts' forecast for the period up to 2020, COPD will become not only one of the most common human diseases, but also one of the leading causes of death. At the same time, the mortality rate from myocardial infarction, cancer, tuberculosis, etc. is expected to decrease.

Key words: COPD, pathology, occurrence, course.

The current concept of COPD, developed by WHO experts (GOLD, 2006), is based on the fact that this disease can be prevented (primary prevention) and successfully treated (secondary prevention). Often, the severity and prognosis of COPD are determined by extrapulmonary manifestations of the disease. It should be emphasized that treatment and prevention programs for COPD largely depend on the comorbidities that it occurs against.

In clinical practice, it is necessary to distinguish between diseases that manifest themselves in the natural course of COPD. These include a group of cardiovascular pathologies, osteoporosis, and others. Another clinical scenario may develop in patients suffering from long-term cardiovascular diseases, which are accompanied by obstructive disorders of the ventilation function of the lungs. Often, the appearance of shortness of breath in this category of patients is associated not so much with cardiac, but with respiratory failure or with combined manifestations of reduced function of both the lungs and the heart.

Among the rather diverse clinical manifestations of COPD, it is necessary to distinguish those stages of the main pathology in which signs of a systemic disease occur. In nature, the inflammatory process is initially localized in the respiratory tract and pulmonary parenchyma, but at certain stages of the disease, its systemic effects are manifested. Tobacco smoking is one of the risk factors contributing to the development and progression of COPD, but it is also associated with the occurrence of pathological processes in the lungs and systemic inflammatory reactions: systemic oxidative stress, vascular endothelial dysfunction, increased activity of procoagulant factors, amplification of oncogenes, and others.

The most common comorbidities in COPD are: cachexia, skeletal muscle hypotrophy and atrophy, arterial hypertension, CHD, heart failure, small circulatory vasculopathy, respiratory tract infections, and cancer.

The prognosis is most unfavorable when COPD is combined with a group of cardiovascular diseases. Patients страдающие with severe forms of COPD are at high risk of sudden death. One of the causes leading to the development of sudden death is a violation of the rhythm. However, in recent years, patients with metabolic syndrome have been singled out. в последние годы стали выделять больных с метаIt is characterized by impaired body weight, abdominal obesity, increased blood triglyceride concentrations, дислипидемией по atherogenic dyslipidemia, increased уровня glucose levels or insulin resistance, prothrombotic and proinflammatory conditions, endothelial dysfunction and a tendency to атеросклеротическому atherosclerotic vascular damage, and increased C - reactive protein concentrations (Figure 8). Among the patients treated with this disease, it is characterized by the following factors: This phenotype includes a high incidence of cardiovascular diseases, especially arterial hypertension (this clinical form of COPD is more common in the female population). Another feature is то, that у in this category of patients в ночной период часто, respiratory arrest is often recorded during the night period остановка. During апнеа, oxygen saturation is significantly reduced. In response to расстройства транспорта oxygen transport disorders формируется, erythrocytosis is formed, as a result of which возрастает вязкость the blood viscosity increases повышается and the tendency to form blood clots increases.

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